

CREAM STRATEGY IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING ENGLISH

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***Abstract:** English language is becoming popular among all over the world. Therefore, the demand for this language is increasing. And some kind of learning strategies are being referenced. CREAM strategy is one of the best example of these strategies .*

***Key words:** strategy, goal, motivation, activity, methods ,idea, assignment.*

C.R.E.A.M is a learning strategy. It is a group of strategies that makes you a successful learner. C.R.E.A.M strategy is a general principle which encourages individuals to constantly stop, think and reflect on ways of improving the way they teach and learn. The main purpose of using this strategy is to nurture, cultivate and develop a sense of responsibility towards effectively learning .And it is a general principle which encourages you to stop, thinking and planning also reflect on ways of improving the way you learn constantly. It analyzes five key aspects needed to be covered while studying .Each letter stands for a type of learning method or methods which we apply to our text. CREAM stands for :

C-Creative

R-Reflective

E-Effective

A-Active

M-Motivated

Here we consider how all of the points above can be applied to language learning .

C-Creativity. The letter “C” stands for the word Creativity. Creativity is an intellectual inventiveness. A creative person has confidence to use individual style in his work. He does not follow the style of others; he applies his own imagination to his learning. Creativity makes you stand out of the crowd. To be a creative person always brain storm individually or in a group, always sketch your ideas on a piece of paper and never be afraid of being different from others. You have the confidence to use your individual strategies and styles, applying imagination to your learning. It encourages you make things independently. Creativity stimulates different areas of the mind , makes learning fresh and effective. It encourages to foster creativity by doing some effective exercises :

- Mixing two different ideas to create something new.
- Finding connection between two random objects.

R-Reflective. The letter “R” stands for Reflective. A reflective person analyzes and evaluates his own performance and draw lessons from it. To be a reflective person one should learn from his past experiences and apply them in future, he should learn from his mistakes and try not to repeat them. Be able to sit with your experience, analyzes and evaluate your own performance and draw lessons from it. It is a very effective habit for learners. Except formal assessment ,they need to reflection on how they learn. Learning journals, self-evolution questions, progress sheets are good tools for reflection.

E-Effective. The letter “E” refers to the word effectiveness. An effective person organizes his space, time and priorities. Effective study skills must be practiced in order to be organized and improve your learning habits and styles. To be an effective learner one should set priorities of what to do first and what can be left for later, always make a schedule to study to save time; always take breaks in between your studies. Does not necessarily mean working hard. Students can spend too many hours working instead of using smart strategies . Organise your space ,time ,priorities, state of mind and resources , to the maximum benefit.

A-Active. The letter ‘A’ stands for Active. Being mental and physical in your learning sense to remain involved in all possible ways with the material. Example "YOU should learn how to be satisfied after working hard and giving everything you have for an assignment". Be personally involved and doing things, physically and mentally, in order to make sense of what you learn .

M-Motivated. The letter ‘M’ stands for ‘Motivated’. Applying goals and tasks that need to be done in order for you generate a path; this allows you to identify the direction in which you want to go resulting in maximum efficiency of the outcome. Example" YOU should always surround yourself with motivate thoughts especially before an exam, because scientist proved that when motivation is high anything is achievable therefore work will be done and quality will be high. Be aware of your own desired outcomes , keep yourself on track using short and long term goals .It is one of the key points which has the greatest influence on the success of learning a language . The primary objective of the strategy is to bring about effective learning while keeping the long term goals in mind. It also helps develop study skills, creativity and motivates them further to get a deeper understanding of what they learn.

ILM – FAN TA'LIMDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR, MUAMMOLAR, TAKLIF VA YECHIMLAR

To come to a conclusion, C-R-E-A-M is a strategic method of learning because it identifies all the aspects that YOU need to identify before you begin studying and afterwards to know if you have covered everything needed. I think that the cream learning strategy can be very helpful and can be a very useful learning style.

References

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